

E-ISSN: 2789-8830
P-ISSN: 2789-8822
Impact Factor (RJIF): 5.62
IJCLLR 2025; 5(2): 302-308
www.civillawjournal.com
Received: 23-08-2025
Accepted: 28-09-2025

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Using basic probability to demonstrate problems with paper printouts from alleged original electronic documents

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DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.22271/civillaw.2025.v5.i2d.171>

Abstract

In 2016, Emmy Award winning host John Oliver reported on the debt-collection industry, in which he exposed fraud being committed on a massive scale. That same fraud-prevalent industry has been the subject of numerous investigations and penalties imposed by the Consumer Financial Protection Bureau (CFPB). Because the fraudulent behaviors of debt collectors have been exposed through lawsuits and reports from various media outlets, debt collectors now employ more sophisticated evidence-manufacturing techniques in pursuit of their collection efforts. Those techniques are so convincing that alleged debtors face resistance from courts that routinely enter adverse judgments based on the manufactured evidence. Insofar as judges are less familiar with metadata in electronic documents but more familiar with traditional mathematical concepts, this paper introduces procedures that use traditional (and relatively simple) mathematics to reliably detect anomalies in manufactured electronic evidence. The procedures identify both within-document and between-document mathematical anomalies.

Keywords: Electronic evidence, Metadata analysis, Probability methods, Fraud detection, Debt-collection litigation

1. Introduction

In 2016, Emmy Award winning host John Oliver^[1] reported on the debt-collection industry, in which he has exposed fraud being committed on a massive scale in that industry^[2]. That same fraud-rife industry has been the subject of numerous investigations and penalties imposed by the Consumer Financial Protection Bureau (CFPB)^[3], whose parent agency is the U.S. Federal Reserve^[4].

Because the fraudulent behaviors of debt collectors have been exposed through lawsuits by the CFPB^[5] and through reports from various media outlets^[6], debt collectors now employ more sophisticated electronic-evidence-manufacturing techniques in pursuit of their debt-collection efforts^[7]. Those techniques are so convincing that alleged debtors face resistance from courts that routinely ignore the anomalies in printed documents and enter judgment against the alleged debtor based on problematic printouts from alleged original electronic files^[8].

Insofar as judges are less familiar with metadata in electronic documents but have sufficient familiarity with traditional mathematics, this paper introduces procedures that use traditional probabilistic mathematics to reliably detect anomalies in paper printouts from alleged original electronic files. In particular, simple probability can be used as a tool to identify between-document mathematical anomalies that demonstrate the likely human or computer intervention prior to printing from an original electronic file.

For purposes of organization, this paper includes the following sections:

- (a) Section 2, discussing probability as a mathematical concept that is applicable to identifying anomalies in printouts of electronic documents;
- (b) Section 3, showing examples from paper printouts of alleged original electronic documents used by debt collectors;
- (c) Section 4, applying simple probability to the paper printouts and explaining why the anomalies demonstrate human or computer intervention (rather than direct printing from the original file);
- (d) Section 5, evidence beyond the documents themselves, which confirm that the documents were indeed made for litigation (and not direct printouts); and
- (e) Section 6, with concluding remarks

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Before continuing, the author wishes to clarify that this paper is applicable only to the legal system in the United States (U.S.), as the author is not a practitioner in any other foreign jurisdiction.

Also, documents from which enlarged portions were copied for the figures are available from publicly filed court documents (as demonstrated from the electronic court stamp on the documents). Because those documents were downloaded from public records (such as court proceedings), the publicly available documents were uploaded and made available for access through a reputable research repository, such as Zenodo (which is used by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA))^[9]. In other words, rather than providing an appendix, citations to the Zenodo links are provided in footnotes, along with citations to the court docket numbers for the cases from which the documents were obtained.

2. Traditional Mathematics used to Identify Anomalies

This Section 2 identifies and explains simple mathematical concepts associated with probability to familiarize the reader before proceeding to subsequent sections that apply the probabilistic mathematics to the paper printouts of alleged electronic documents.

Probability is the quantification of the likelihood (or odds) that an event or a set of events will occur^[10]. Thus, by way of example, if there are two (2) equally possible outcomes, such as in flipping a coin (i.e., heads or tails), then the likelihood of one of those outcomes is 1/2 (fractionally) or 0.5 (in decimal form) or fifty-percent (50%, in percent)^[11]. Likewise, if there are six (6) possible outcomes, such as in rolling a die (i.e., 1 through 6 pips), then the likelihood of one of those outcomes is 1/6, or 0.167 (rounded to the thousandth decimal place), or 16.7% (rounded to the tenth decimal place)^[12].

Simply stated, for n equally likely outcomes within a single event (with n being an integer), the probability of one (1) particular outcome is:

$$1 / n \quad \text{Eq. 1.}$$

In the event that repeatable events are studied, the probability of that same event occurring independently is simply an exponential progression of the original probability, as follows:

$$(1 / n)^m \quad \text{[Eq. 2],}$$

with n being the total number of possibilities within a single event and m being the number of independent events. For example, the probability of five (5) sequential heads occurring in five (5) independent coin flips is:

$$(0.5)^5 = 0.03125 \quad \text{[Eq. 3],}$$

or 3.125%. Similarly, the probability of rolling 1-pip sequentially in three (3) independent rolls of the die are:

$$(0.167)^3 = 0.00462 \quad \text{[Eq. 4],}$$

or 0.462% (which is less than a half of a percent).

This same mathematic principle applies when analyzing entries across multiple independent printouts from multiple

independent electronic documents. For example, if there are twenty-six (26) equally possible lines printed from an alleged database or spreadsheet, then the probability that a particular entry appears in, for example, line sixteen (16) without any intervention or deliberate skewing (by human hands or computer program) is:

$$1 / 26 = 0.0384 \quad \text{[Eq. 5],}$$

which is 3.84%. The probability that another entry from a different independent document appears on that same line 16 of 26 is:

$$(0.0384)^2 = 0.00148 \quad \text{[Eq. 6],}$$

and the probability that the entries in four (4) independent documents all appear on that same line 16 of 26 is:

$$(0.0384)^4 = 2.188 \times 10^{-6} \quad \text{[Eq. 7],}$$

or 1 in 456,976.

Similarly, if there are twenty-one (21) equally possible lines printed from an alleged database or spreadsheet, then the probability that a particular entry appears in, for example, line eleven (11) of 21 is:

$$1 / 21 = 0.0476 \quad \text{[Eq. 8],}$$

which is 4.76%. The probability that the entry is in that same line 11 of 21 across seven (7) independent documents is:

$$(0.0476)^7 = 5.55 \times 10^{-10} \quad \text{[Eq. 9],}$$

or 1 in 1,801,088,541.

In the context of legal cases in which consumers are being sued based on printouts of alleged bank documents, this calculation of probability permits comparison of multiple independent printouts side-by-side, which can demonstrate anomalies and problematic aspects of the printouts. For example, if account information for a particular debtor in a consumer debt-collection case is expected to appear in a random line number on a one-page printout, then one would not expect the pertinent information to appear on the same line across every independent one-page printout. Consequently, applying simple probability provides a reliable method of confirming whether or not there has been any intervention (by a human or a computer) to force the information-of-interest in a particular printout to consistently appear on the same line across multiple documents.

3. Manufactured Evidence to Which Mathematics Are Applied

With the mathematical concepts explained, this Section 3 reproduces and enlarges several excerpts from printouts that have been filed in various courts. The enlarged portions are shown as figure inserts, with their respective corresponding full documents cited as downloadable links in footnotes. For purposes of illustration, added to each of the excerpts is a clear indication of the line in which the relevant information is found in the printout (e.g., "Line 11"). Also, for consistency, the examples herein are documents from one

(1) particular entity (namely, LVNV Funding, LLC (hereinafter, "LVNV")) filed in one (1) particular jurisdiction (namely, the Municipal Court of Hamilton County, Ohio, U.S.A.)^[13]. However, the same mathematical principles apply to correspondingly similar multi-line documents from other similar entities that have been filed in other jurisdictions^[14].

With this in mind, the documents for analysis in this paper were obtained from *LVNV Funding, LLC v. Tamika Brown*, Case Number 24CV01441 (Municipal Court, Hamilton County, Ohio) (hereinafter, "Brown Case"); *LVNV Funding, LLC v. Nancy Duvall*, Case Number 23CV28211 (Municipal Court, Hamilton County, Ohio) (hereinafter, "Duvall Case"); *LVNV Funding, LLC v. Henry Flowers*, Case Number 24CV21667 (Municipal Court, Hamilton Count,

Ohio) (hereinafter, "Flowers Case"); *LVNV Funding, LLC v. Paul Loveless*, Case Number 24CV17562 (Municipal Court, Hamilton County, Ohio) (hereinafter, "Loveless Case"); *LVNV Funding, LLC v. Eileen Pike*, Case Number 23CV28432 (Municipal Court, Hamilton County, Ohio) (hereinafter, "Pike Case"); *LVNV Funding, LLC v. Damien Townsend*, Case Number 23CV28432 (Municipal Court, Hamilton County, Ohio) (hereinafter, "Townsend Case"); and *LVNV Funding, LLC v. Baron Wynter*, Case Number 24CV21026 (Municipal Court, Hamilton County, Ohio) (hereinafter, "Wynter Case") (collectively, "LVNV Cases").

Excerpts of the relevant file from these cases are shown here:

LineNumber	FirstName	LastName	CurrentBalanceOwing	ChargeOffAmount
2156	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2157	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2158	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2159	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2160	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2161	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2162	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2163	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2164	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2165	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2166	TAMIKA	BROWN	1862.9200	1862.92
2167	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2168	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2169	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2170	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2171	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2172	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2173	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2174	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2175	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
2176	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

11th Line

[15]

LineNumber	CHNAME	BALANCE	Cur_Bal
1523	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1524	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1525	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1526	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1527	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1528	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1529	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1530	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1531	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1532	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1533	DUVALL,NANCY	\$1,450.92	1450.9200
1534	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1535	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1536	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1537	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1538	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1539	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1540	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1541	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1542	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1543	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

11th Line

[16]

LineNumber	BrwrFirstName	BrwrLastName	PurchaseBalance	ChgOffBalance	PurchaseIntBal	ChgOffInt
230	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
231	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
232	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
233	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
234	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
235	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
236	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
237	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
238	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
239	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
240	HENRY	FLOWERS	1257.350	1257.35	77.650	77.65
241	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
242	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
243	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
244	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
245	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
246	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
247	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
248	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
249	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
250	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

11th Line

[17]

LineNumber	FirstName	LastName	CurrentBalanceOwing
3141	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3142	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3143	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3144	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3145	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3146	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3147	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3148	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3149	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3150	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3151	PAUL	LOVELESS	900.4200
3152	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3153	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3154	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3155	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3156	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3157	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3158	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3159	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3160	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
3161	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

11th Line

[18]

LineNumber	first_name	last_name
341	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
342	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
343	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
344	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
345	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
346	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
347	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
348	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
349	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
350	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
351	Eileen	Pike
352	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
353	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
354	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
355	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
356	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
357	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
358	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
359	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
360	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
361	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

11th Line

[19]

LineNumber	CHNAME	COAMOUNT	Cur_Bal
1960	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1961	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1962	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1963	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1964	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1965	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1966	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1967	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1968	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1969	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1970	TOWNSEND,DAMIEN	\$1,333.10	1333.1000
1971	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1972	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1973	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1974	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1975	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1976	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1977	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1978	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1979	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
1980	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

11th Line

[20]

LineNumber	CHNAME	HIGHBALANCE	COAMOUNT	Cur_Bal	LastPurchaseAmount
26309	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26310	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26311	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26312	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26313	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26314	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26315	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26316	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26317	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26318	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26319	WYNTER,BARON	\$637.67	\$637.67	637.6700	58.3700
26320	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26321	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26322	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26323	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26324	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26325	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26326	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26327	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26328	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]
26329	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]	[Redacted]

11th Line

[21]

4. Mathematical Analysis of Manufactured Evidence

This Section 4 straightforwardly applies the mathematical concepts from Section 2 to the enlarged portions of the printouts from Section 3. Additionally, this Section 4 explains (in as simple terms as possible) how traditional probability demonstrates that there was some intervention or tampering (either by a human or by a computer program) before generating the actual printed documents (rather than the original electronic file being directly printed to paper). Unexplainable anomalies and unlikely odds are analyzed mathematically without referencing metadata or underlying document properties, even though the underlying document properties eventually reinforces that the printed documents are fabricated (as shown in Section 5, *infra*).^[22]

With this in mind, to set up the probabilistic analysis, the relevant portions of the documents are the first ten (10) lines and the last ten (10) lines in the LVNV Files, which ubiquitously recite "[Redacted]." ^[23] Thus, the only relevant line is 11 of 21 in every one of the LVNF Files. Thus, the mathematical probability of Brown being on line 11 of 21 is 1 in 21, ^[24] which standing alone is not peculiar because the entry must appear on one of the lines. Even having two (2) relevant entries (e.g., Brown and Duvall) on the same line 11 of 21 ^[25] is explainable, even with odds of 1 in 441. Three (3) relevant entries (e.g., Brown, Duvall, and Flowers) all being on the same line (11 of 21) ^[26] becomes a bit more problematic, with odds of 1 in 9,261, but not disturbingly impossible.

However, as additional entries emerge in which the only relevant line is 11 of 21, the mathematical probability progresses toward impossibility. For example, at four (4) identically placed entries (e.g., Brown, Duvall, Flowers, and Loveless) on line 11 of 21, ^[27] the probability drops to 1 in 194,481. At five (e.g., Brown, Duvall, Flowers, Loveless, and Pike), ^[28] the odds drop to 1 in 4,084,101. At six (e.g., Brown, Duvall, Flowers, Loveless, Pike, and Townsend), ^[29] the mathematical probability is now 1 in 85,766,121. Considering only seven (e.g., Brown, Duvall, Flowers, Loveless, Pike, Townsend, and Wynter), ^[30] the probability drops to 1 in 801,088,541 (which is nearly three (3) times worse than the odds of winning the PowerBall® Grand Prize)^[31].

When there are more than forty (40) total LVNV Files, all of which uniformly have twenty-one (21) total substantive lines with only line 11 being the operative line in all of the forty (40) LVNF Files, the mathematical probability becomes:

$$(1/21)^{40} = 1.29 \times 10^{-53} \tag{Eq. 10},$$

which, for all practical purposes, is so astronomically small as to be considered a mathematical impossibility. Considering probability alone, the between-document mathematical anomaly demonstrates that the LVNV Files cannot be direct printouts of the alleged original electronic file. In other words, problematic aspects of printed evidence can be uncovered without the need to rely on specialized information that is available only from the metadata of the original electronic files.

5. Confirmation That the Evidence was Manufactured

From a scientific standpoint, mathematics alone should be sufficient to conclude with a reasonable degree of certainty that documents are not directly printed without intervention from an original electronic file. The additional step of concluding that the documents are manufactured for litigation is confirmed by sworn testimony from the debt collectors themselves, such as Asset Acceptance, LLC (hereinafter, "Asset") and LVNV.

For example, when confronted with alleged printouts in which every relevant entry fell on line 16 of 26, at least two (2) representatives from Asset testified under oath that the paper printouts were made-for-litigation documents^[32].

The corporate representative for LVNV provided additional information about the original electronic files, which confirmed that the paper documents were not direct printouts from the original electronic files. Specifically, LVNV confirmed that: (a) the original files from the banks are text files (meaning, ASCII files with no style or layout formatting); and (b) the original ASCII files are not reformatted for appearance or ease-of-use ^[33]. As such, the LVNV representative testimony reinforces the fact that the style-and-layout formatted LVNV Files shown in Section 3 are manufactured documents (and not original ASCII-formatted bank files).

6. Conclusion

As demonstrated in this paper, when the bench and bar (having less familiarity with metadata in electronic documents) must determine whether or not paper copies are direct printouts of alleged original electronic files, there are reliable and time-tested mathematical tools available to assist in that determination.

This paper has identified and applied simple probabilistic mathematics to reliably detect anomalies in printouts from electronic files, especially when one knows *a priori* how certain electronic documents must be formatted due to regulations in the industry. The mathematical procedures explained herein can be used to identify between-document mathematical anomalies, thereby reinforcing the reasonableness of conclusions about the integrity of paper printouts from electronic files.

Insofar as the results and conclusions from the probabilistic analyses have been confirmed by sworn testimony, it is clear that simple probability can be applied to detect patterns that suggest (more likely than not) that evidence has been manufactured. At its core, because basic mathematics (as used in the processes that are described herein) have been time-tested and shown to be reliable, these mathematical approaches can be implemented independently or in conjunction with metadata analysis as a redundancy.

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